

Organization Identifiers

A decision tree to distinguish between the different types of organization identifier (OrgID) to use in a research repository, grants database, publishing workflow or other type of administrative system. The tree covers various considerations which were identified by FREYA partners as affecting their choice of identifier. Some identifiers are suitable for more than one purpose and some identifiers can be implemented in the same way and have similar coverage, therefore some of these options repeat.

Why do you want an organization identifier?

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ROR

ROR is the Research Organization Registry. It is an open identifier for organizations available through a CC0 licence. It is meant as a "linking identifier," and does not aim to replace other types of identifiers but is designed primarily for matching affiliations on research publications. Launched in January 2019, it is accessible by API, data dump and through a web interface ror.org. Using GRID as the seed database, Crossref and DataCite support ROR within their metadata schemas. ROR has been developed as a community effort from DataCite, Crossref, Digital Science and California Digital Library.

Format: <https://ror.org/04wxnsj81>

Crossref Funder ID

Crossref's Funder ID is a DOI assigned to organizations which provide grants or awards. Elsevier donated the registry to Crossref in 2012 who maintain it and make it available under a CC0 licence and provide a search interface, data dump and an API to access it.

Format: [10.13039/100010269](https://doi.org/10.13039/100010269)

ISNI €

ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier, ISO 277729). It is designed to identify the public identity of persons and organizations and was conceived from the library and rights management community and the database has a high standard of curation. ISNI will be available in early 2020 via linked open data formats under CC0 as well as records for individual download.

Format: [0000 0001 2308 1542](https://isni.org/0000-0001-2308-1542)

PSI €

This ID is used to identify academic institutions in the thelPRegistry.org. It has been primarily used by librarians and publishers used to provide and designate access control.

GRID €

GRID (Global Research Identifier Database) was launched by Digital Science in 2015. It is available through API, web interface and data dump under a CC0 licence. It was designed by Digital Science to meet the use cases from their products, primarily affiliation matching.

Format: grid.475826.a

LEI €

The Legal Entity Identifier was created after the global financial crisis and aims to identify entities who are involved in financial transactions internationally.

Format: [549300YQJZ9YPHW5V73](https://www.lei.org/549300YQJZ9YPHW5V73)

Ringgold ID €

Ringgold is an ISNI Registration Agency but also maintains the Ringgold ID which is an identifier designed for entities in the publishing lifecycle. Ringgold does not provide a data dump or an open searchable interface or an API. A limited search service is available after a registration has been purchased.

Format: [RIN 5072](https://www.ringgold.com/RIN5072)

Wikidata

Wikidata is a project to create an open knowledge database focused on entities. Each entry in the database is assigned a QID that is unique and is language independent. It is the source of Wikimedia projects such as Wikipedia. It is released under a public domain licence and offers a SPARQL query service.

Format: [Q821542](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q821542)

€ Membership/Subscription Fees

All services with this symbol charge some sort of membership or subscription fee for full access to the service. Full access can include features such as minting the PIDs and API access. These fees can vary depending on the service and the type of organisation who wishes to use them. Many of the PID services which do not have membership or subscription fees require more technical resources from your organisation to set up and maintain the service.

For more information on Organization Identifiers

- FREYA Knowledge Hub page on New Types of Persistent Identifier
<https://www.pidforum.org/t/newtypes-of-persistent-identifiers/743>
- D4.4 Organizational IDs in Practice
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666255>

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The FREYA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 777523.